

Graphene coated natural fiber composites for marine applications

Khurshid Malik, Mohamed Loukil, Marie Jonsson, Erik Khranovsky, Mykhailo Zhybak, Robin Wikström

Motivation

Sustainability

Natural fibers:
Flax Fibers

**Very sensitive
to water and
humidity**

Project Aim

Investigate how coating natural fibers with graphene affects their sensitivity to water and performance.

A complete study from the microscale to the macroscale level

- Material Selection
- Manufacturing
- Testing
- Material characterization

Outline

Cupon tests

Purpose: Impact of graphene coating in surface layers of full.

- Water absorption
- Visual inspection

Graphene amount comparison (coupon)

Purpose: Optimise graphene amount

- Water absorption
- Visual inspection
- Mechanical testing
- SEM

Small hatch demonstrator

Purpose: Scalability

- Water absorption
- Visual inspection

Composite design

Coating:

- Graphene flakes coating by Grafren AB purification technology

Material System

- Flax Fiber weaves
- Polymer matrix: SR InfuGreen (Bioresin)

Manufacturing

- Vacuum Infusion

Testing and Analysis

- Physical : Fiber volume fraction and Voids
- Mechanical: Flexural, Tensile, ILSS
- Failure: Visual, SEM
- Hot Salted Water, 50°C

No Coated
0% coated

Surface Layers Coated
25% coated

All Coated
100% coated

Graphene coating process

(proprietary Grafren AB)

1.

Aqueous dispersions of few-layer graphene flakes (graphene powder in deionized water without any surfactants or chemical binders). Ultrasonic homogenization for 30–60 minutes.

2.

Flax fabric immersion at room temperature. Graphene flakes adhere to the fiber surfaces through van der Waals interactions, forming a non-continuous but conformal coating.

3.

Fibers are removed and air-dried under ambient conditions or oven-dried at 60 °C to remove residual moisture.

Reference:

<https://patents.google.com/patent/SE544448C2/fr>

Composite manufacturing

Quasi-isotropic [+45/-45/0/90]s
Infusion

Water absorption properties

Salt water 50 °C

8
Fiber swelling/
degradation

No Coated

No Coated-Conditioned

All Coated

All Coated-Conditioned

-> Water resistance were improved slightly incoated laminates.

Graphene Amount comparison

Lay-up: ($\pm 45/\pm 45/\pm 45/\pm 45$)

Plate size: 250 x 160 mm²

Graphene (wt.%) at 4 different concentrations:

- 0%
- 0.5%
- 1.0%
- 1.5%

Flexural Properties for Different Graphene Amounts

Sample Name		FS (MPa)	Strain (%)	FM (GPa)
Pure	0.0	105.6±0.2	5.4±0.6	3.9±0.1
Full Graphene	0.5	87.1±0.4	4.6±0.3	3.9±0.1
Full Graphene	1.0	72.8±3.0	5.3±0.9	2.8±0.2
Full Graphene	1.5	145.4±13.3	4.2±0.5	5.8±0.3

FS: Flexural Strength, FM: Flexural Modulus

SEM analysis - fibers

Smooth surface

0% graphene

Uniform coating

1.5% graphene

1.5% of Graphene: The fibers were fully coated without any sign of detachment of graphene flakes

SEM analysis - composite laminate

0% graphene

1.5% graphene

Small Demonstrator (Hatch)

Manufacturing setup

Not Coated

100% coated fibers
(1.5%)

Hatch demo testing (salt water immersion)

Before water absorption test

After water absorption test

Uncoated

Fiber swelling/
degradation

Coated

Conclusions and future prospects

- Graphene coating successfully applied to flax fiber, enhancing composite performance.
- 1.5 wt.% graphene coating resulted in approximately 38% increase in flexural strength and a 48% rise in flexural modulus.
- The testing at the demonstrator level (Hatch) confirmed around 40% improvement in water resistance.
- To fully harness the potential of graphene in bio-composites, the following key factors are currently under investigation:
 - Graphene size, thickness, concentration and surface area
 - Desired coating thickness and Post-coating drying process
- Larger demonstrator will be manufactured
 - The fabrication process will utilize prepreg to ensure consistency and quality.

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Contact:

Marie Jonsson, marie.s.jonsson@se (Presenter)

Khurshid Malik khurshid.malik@liu.se (Post-
doctoral researcher)

Mohamed Sahbi Loukil mohammad.loukil@liu.se
(Principal investigator)